

The Ayuwang Monastery 阿育王寺

Secondary source

Entered by Yi Liu, University of Arizona

* Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA

Entry tags: Religious Group, China, Monastery, Buddhist Traditions, Language, Unknown, Religious Place

The Ayuwang monastery is located in the western foothill of Mount Mao 鄞 in present-day Ningbo 寧波. The origin story of this monastery recounts the legend of Liu Sahe 劉薩訶 (alt. 劉薩何), also known by his dharma name Huida 慧達. Legend has it that he encountered a deity in the netherworld and subsequently revived to worship the Aśoka stūpas as an act of repentance. According to the Ji Shenzhou sanbao gantong lu 集神州三寶感通錄 (comp. 664), upon arriving in Mao county in 281 CE, Liu Sahe heard the sound of a bell at midnight and witnessed the emergence of a śāriṃa stūpa from underground. Historical records from the Datang Yuezhou dudufu Maoxian Ayuwang si changzhutian bei 大唐越州都督府鄞縣阿育王寺常住田碑 (833) and the Sheli baota zhuan 舍利寶塔傳 (972) document the establishment of this monastery in 405 CE to protect the śāriṃa stūpa. During Emperor Wu 武 of Liang's 梁 reign (502-549), the monastery underwent expansion, acquiring more buildings and arable lands through imperial patronage. An official plaque inscribed with "Ayuwang si 阿育王寺" was granted, naming this monastery after King Aśoka of the Maurya Empire due to the śāriṃa stūpa's association with Aśoka's distribution of the Buddha's relics in Buddhist tradition. Although the Ayuwang monastery declined during wartime chaos, it was later restored, regaining significance as an influential site in the seventh century. As the cult of the śāriṃa stūpa became popularized during the Tang dynasty (618-907), this monastery received substantial support from patrons of diverse social standings and developed local power in the southeast region. In the tenth century, the śāriṃa stūpa preserved in the Ayuwang monastery was relocated to Hangzhou by the order of Wuyue ruler Qian Chu 錢俶 (r. 947-978) and subsequently transported to the Northern Song capital in Kaifeng. In 1008, the Song court granted the Ayuwang monastery an imperial plaque, renaming it "Guangli 廣利," and restructuring it into a "ten directions Chan monastery" (shifang chancha 十方禪刹). Prior to this change, the Ayuwang monastery was recognized for its emphasis on Vinaya teachings, with monk Huize 慧則 (835-908) serving as the abbot. The connection with Baoyun Yitong 寶雲義通 (927-988) indicated the dissemination of Tiantai 天台 teachings within this monastery. Since its transformation into a Chan monastery, prominent Chan masters, such as Dajue Huailian 大覺懷璉 (1010-1090), Zhenxie Qingliao 真歇清了 (1088-1151), and Dahui Zonggao 大慧宗杲 (1089-1163), made significant efforts to elevate the prestige of this monastery. Visits by Japanese Buddhist monks, such as Chōgen 重源 (1121-1206) and Myōan Eisai 明庵榮西 (1141-1215), extended the Ayuwang monastery's fame overseas. In the thirteenth century, the Ayuwang monastery obtained imperial recognition as one of the "Five Mountains." Meanwhile, the cult of the śāriṃa stūpa in Ayuwang monastery further expanded as a result of its divine manifestations exhibited in the imperial courts of Southern Song and Yuan. In 1382, this monastery received the official title "Ayuwang chansi 阿育王禪寺" from the Ming court and reinstated its religious rank as the fifth among the Five Mountains of Chan school. Despite experiencing multiple destruction and subsequent rebuilding, the Ayuwang monastery continues to endure as a renowned Buddhist site to this day.

Date Range: 400 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Ayuwang Monastery

Region tags: China

Yinzhou 鄞州 district, Ningbo 寧波, Zhejiang 浙江 province, China

参与者地位

✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

一般变量

来源与发掘

书面资料来源

用以理解这个题目的书面资料来源

—来源1: Guo Zizhang 郭子章. Ayuwang shan si zhi 阿育王山寺志. In Zhongguo fosizhi congkan 中國佛寺志叢刊, edited by Bai Huawen 白化文 and Zhang Zhi 張智, vol. 89-90. Yangzhou: Guangling shushe, 2006.

—来源2: Shi Wanquan 釋畹荃. Mingzhou Ayuwang shan zhi xu 明州阿育王山志續. In Zhongguo Fosi Shizhi Huikan 中國佛寺史志彙刊, edited by Du Jiexiang 杜潔祥, vol. 12. Taipei: Mingwen shuju, 1980-1994.

在线来源

用以理解这个题目的在线来源

—来源1 URL: <http://buddhisticinformatics.dila.edu.tw/fosizhi/ui.html?book=g010>

—来源1 描述: Gazetteer of the Ayuwang Monastery in Mingzhou 明州阿育王山志 (A temple gazetteer compiled in the Ming dynasty.)

—来源2 URL: <http://buddhisticinformatics.dila.edu.tw/fosizhi/ui.html?book=g011>

—来源2 描述: Continued Gazetteer of the Ayuwang Monastery in Mingzhou 明州阿育王山續志 (Compiled in the Qing dynasty as a supplement to the Ming version.)

—来源3 URL: <https://nrs.lib.harvard.edu/urn-3:fhcl:4740529>

—来源3 描述: Gazetteer of the Ayuwang Monastery in Mingzhou, 10 vol. Continued Gazetteer, 6 vol. 明州阿育王山志: 十卷, 續志六卷.

Notes: A map of the Ayuwang monastery and an image of the Aśoka stūpa can be found in the Mingzhou Ayuwang shanzhi 明州阿育王山志 in seq. 34-35.

<https://id.lib.harvard.edu/alma/990129537720203941/catalog> Inscription of the śāriira stūpa in the Ayuwang monastery 阿育王寺舍利宝塔碑 (The rubbing of a stone stele inscribed in 1884 CE.)

https://khirin-ld.rekihaku.ac.jp/rdf/nmjh_kaken_medInterNationalExcange/E14403 Prayer text of Song dynasty pilgrims in the Yuwang monastery 宋人參詣医王山之時禮拜文 (A Song-dynasty manuscript of ritual text chanted by pilgrims worshipping the śāriira stūpa in the Ayuwang monastery.)

这个地方曾经是发掘重点吗 (古代、违法的、科学的) ?

给每个年代或者发掘类型回答‘是’

— 否

地形背景

地点是否与景点要素相关联

—其他【请注明】: Mountain

Notes: The Ayuwang monastery is located in the Yuwang 育王 Peak of the Mao 鄞 Mountains.

除了结构之外，这个地方是否涉及人造特征：

其他特征可能包括空地，梯田，当地环境的其他整改。

一是

特征类型

— 地面平整

— 空地

— 轨道或路面

— 水的特点

— 种植

Notes: Statistics show that the contemporary Ayuwang Monastery covers an area of 80,000 square meters, in which the floor area is 14,000 square meters. The monastery complex includes buildings, ponds, forests, and parking lots. (source: https://www.nbyz.gov.cn/art/2022/3/10/art_1229240804_54660210.html)

这个地方是否位于城市或显著城市化的地区：

一是

这个地方和城市结构之间是否有明显的界限：

— 是

Notes: The location of Ayuwang monastery is near the highway connecting the centers between the Yinzhou 鄞州 district and the Beilun 北仑 district of Ningbo 宁波.

这个地方是否明显位于城市结构中：

这个地方是否位于中心位置，或重要通道的十字路口？

— 否

这个地方是否在乡村的环境中：

一是

Notes: In Wuxiang 五乡 town of the Yinzhou 鄞州 district.

这个地方附近有定居点吗：

— 是

这个地方附近有旅行路线吗：

— 我不知道

这个地方是否远离非宗教的居住地点：

— 否

结构存在

是否有结构/特征表现：

说明：对每个结构/特征或群组的答案可以不同。

— 是

Notes: This monastery complex follows the structure of Buddhist monasteries in Chinese tradition.

↳ 单一结构

— 是

Notes: The monastery layout is symmetric based on buildings located on the central axis, which include the front gate, the pond, the hall of heavenly kings, the Mahavira hall, the hall of śarīra, and the scripture depository.

↳ 结构有明确形状

— 长方形

↳ 单一特征

— 空地

Notes: A courtyard exists in the front of each main building.

↳ 一组结构：

— 是

Notes: The main buildings on the central axis are surrounded by two smaller buildings on both sides to constitute the "quadrangular enclosure."

↳ 它们是否是单一设计/施工阶段的一部分：

— 是

↳ 一组特征：

— 是

Notes: The compound of the Upper Pagoda located outside the Ayuwang monastery while the compound of the West Pagoda and the East Pagoda located in the monastery.

↳ 它们是否是单一设计/施工阶段的一部分：

— 否

↳ 它是一个更大地方/圣所的一部分
— 否

↳ 结构/特征或者群组的功能是什么：
给每一个明显的功能回答一次“是”
— 崇拜

↳ 崇拜：

— 公共的

Notes: For visitors to show reverence for Buddhist divinities.

— 纪念的

Notes: To perform rituals dedicated to divinities enshrined in the buildings.

↳ 结构/特征是否完成：
— 是

↳ 结构/特征是否计划持续超过一代：
— 是

↳ 结构/特征是否随时间而改变：
— 是

Notes: In different historical times, new buildings were established based on the needs for holding more visitors and incorporating prevalent cults of various Buddhist divinities.

↳ 结构/特征是否被摧毁：
— 是

↳ 结构/特征是怎么被摧毁的
— 烧掉

Notes: Due to the chaos of war, the Ayuwang monastery was destroyed by fire several times in its history.

↳ 是被故意摧毁的吗：
— 是战争的结果

↳ 因为事故/自然现象被摧毁：
— 人为事故

↳ 结构/特征是否被重建
— 是

↳ 在古代
— 多于一次

↳ 现代
— 后文艺复兴

Notes: The contemporary Ayuwang monastery was reconstructed from 1978 to 1992.

创作/建构/奉献的原因

这个地方是否被用于对非人类超自然存在的崇拜/沟通：
— 是

↳ 致力于一种超自然的存在：
— 否

↳ 致力于多于一种的超自然存在：
— 是【请注明】：Visitors worship varied Buddhist divinities enshrined in different halls, especially the śarīra stūpa preserved in the śarīra hall.

这个地方是用来崇拜半神人类的吗：
— 否

这个地方是用来崇拜非神祖先的吗？
— 是

Notes: The hall of patriarchs has the memorial tablets in reverence of deceased Buddhist masters.

↳ 他是一个纪念碑吗：
— 否

↳ 这是对一个家庭/宗族/群体的纪念吗？
— 是

Notes: Buddhist masters of specific dharma lineage.

这个地方是由一个官方政体委托建造/建造的吗：

政体是一个利用劳动力的地方权力机制。

— 是

Notes: In ancient times, the Ayuwang monastery was established and reconstructed based on edicts of the imperial court. The construction project of contemporary Ayuwang monastery was initiated and founded by the government of China.

↳ 注明

— 王或者皇帝

结构是由特定组群的人建造的吗：

— 是

↳ 群体

— 特别老公/手艺人

此地被认为起源于神圣干涉的结果：

— 是

Notes: According to the Ji Shenzhou Sanbao gantong lu 集神州三寶感通錄, Liu Sahe 劉薩何 returned from the netherworld and met a monk who instructed him to find the Aśoka stūpa in Kuaiji 會稽 to make repentance and eliminate his sins. When searching for the Aśoka stūpa, Liu Sahe heard the sound of the bell from underground at midnight. In three days, he saw the stūpa and śarīra emerge on the ground.

↳ 注明

— 由其他超自然存在（们）披露【请注明】：The śarīra stūpa

这个地方是被创造用于标记或纪念一个超自然存在或者人类的诞生地吗：

— 否

此地是作为一个事件的结果被创造的吗：

— 是

Notes: The Ayuwang monastery was established to preserve the śarīra stūpa which was believed to have emerged at this site.

↳ 注明

— 奇迹

此地的创立是否由外部资金或者物质捐助：

— 是

Notes: According to the Sheli baota zhuan 舍利寶塔傳, in 405 CE emperor An 安 of Jin 晉 provided imperial support to build a monastery and approved the ordination of twenty seven monks to send them to this monastery.

↳ 对于同一个宗教团体/传统的赞助是否作为此地的主要用法：

— 是

Notes: Patronage for Buddhist monks who dwelled in the Ayuwang monastery and performed rituals as offerings to the śāriṃa stūpa.

此地的建设是否由以下因素促动：

— 其他【请注明】：To protect and preserve the śāriṃa stūpa.

此地特别为存放经典/神经经文准备的吗：

— 否

Notes: Normally, Buddhist scriptures were bestowed to the Ayuwang monastery by the imperial court. The depository of Buddhist scriptures in contemporary Ayuwang monastery has a collection of the Qianlong Tripiṭaka.

设计和材料依然存在

整体结构

这个地方是否由多重结构组成：

— 是

↳ 任何结构附属风景或者于风景特征相关联吗：

— 是

Notes: Four ponds and three forests areas in the Ayuwang monastery.

↳ 任何结构附属其他结构吗：

— 是

↳ 在结构中有阶级吗：

— 是

Notes: The hierarchy of guardian deities and other Buddhist divinities.

纪念建筑存在吗：

在这里，纪念性建筑被定义为超过平均人类比例的建筑结构，并且通常比实现结构的实用功能所需的更大且更复杂。纪念碑建筑的例子包括美索不达米亚金字塔，埃及金字塔，希腊和罗马神庙，中美洲金字塔，北美和爱琴海墓葬等。

一是

Notes: Three pagodas of the Ayuwang monastery. The Upper Pagoda and the West Pagoda are Yuan-dynasty architecture. The East Pagoda was built in the 1990s.

↳ 在平均水平地区，有多少百分比的区域被用作建造纪念碑：
— 我不知道

↳ 最大的单体宗教纪念碑痕迹，平方米：
如已知，请在评论中添加尺寸。
— 我不知道

↳ 最大的单体宗教纪念碑高度，米
— 高度，米: 53
Notes: The height of the East Pagoda.

↳ 平均纪念碑的尺寸，平方米：
— 我不知道

↳ 平均纪念碑高度，米
— 高度，米: 40
Notes: The height of the Upper Pagoda and the West Pagoda is 30 meters and 36 meters.

结构/特征由自然材料组成吗：

针对每个材料类型回答【是】

一是

↳ 土
— 是

↳ 材料来源于地方吗：
— 是

↳ 材料是否在地方自然环境中缺乏：
— 否

↳ 沙子
— 我不知道

↳ 陶土
— 我不知道

↳ 石膏
— 我不知道

↳ 木头
— 是

↳ 材料来源于地方吗：
— 我不知道

↳ 材料是否在地方自然环境中缺乏：
— 否

↳ 草
— 是

↳ 材料来源于地方吗：
— 是

↳ 材料是否在地方自然环境中缺乏：
— 否

↳ 石头
— 是

Notes: Stone steles preserved in the Ayuwang monastery.

↳ 材料来源于地方吗：
— 是

↳ 材料是否在地方自然环境中缺乏：
— 否

↳ 其他

—其他【请注明】：The spring (Miaoxi spring 妙喜泉)。

结构/特征由人工材料组成吗：

—是【请注明】：Bricks

装饰

装饰存在吗

—是

↳ 是大楼的装饰部分吗（永久）：

—是

↳ 在外部

—是

Notes: Decorations on the roof of buildings.

↳ 在内部

—是

Notes: Interior decorations of the buildings.

↳ 装饰附属属于大楼，比如可移动浮雕作品或者壁毯

—是

Notes: The scrolls of paintings hung on the east and west wall of the śarīra hall.

↳ 装饰是具象的吗：

一种具象的表现在这里是指包含清楚的人物、拟人化的、动物或者动物形的形式。通常，它区分有生命的和没有生命的存在，也区分叙述叙事构成和静物、风景、抽象概念等等。针对每一种被描绘的形象回答【是】

—是

↳ 有上帝被描绘吗：

—否

↳ 有其他超自然存在被描绘吗：

—是

Notes: The moldings of vajra-wielding deities on the roof.

↳ 有人被描绘吗：

— 是

Notes: Images of humans on the decorative board of the roof.

↳ 有动物被描绘吗：

— 是

Notes: The moldings in the shape of dragons, elephants and other mythical animals on the roof (jishou 脊獸).

↳ 有动物和人的混合体被描绘吗：

— 是

Notes: One of the moldings on the ridge portrays the immortal riding a phoenix.

↳ 装饰是非具象的吗：

— 是

↳ 它是不是几何/抽象的

— 是

Notes: The cintāmaṇi jewel decorated on the central roof of the śarīra hall. Geometric designs can also be found on the roof.

↳ 花形主题

— 是

Notes: Flowers depicted on the decorative boards on the roof.

↳ 它是不是文字/书法

— 是

Notes: Characters on the roof of buildings, for example, the roof of the śarīra hall has four characters saying "Buddhist Land in the Southeast" (dongnan fogueo 東南佛國).

↳ 其他【请注明】

—其他【请注明】：The shape of ridges.

↳ 装饰被隐藏或者有观赏限制吗：

— 否

↳ 有雕像展示吗：

— 是

↳ 异教雕像
— 否

↳ 上帝/超自然存在的雕像
— 是

Notes: The statues of Buddhist divinities in the buildings.

↳ 人类的雕像
— 是

Notes: The statue of Buddhist monk Jianzhen 鉴真 (688-763) in the hall of shelidan 舍利单.

↳ 其他【请注明】

—其他【请注明】: Statues of animals.

↳ 有其他浮雕出现吗：

和雕刻在圆形体上的雕塑相反，浮雕其中人物从背景支撑物，通常是平坦的表面突出。浮雕可以从石头、陶土、或者类似材料中雕刻出来。

— 是

↳ 浮雕展现在此地被崇拜的上帝：

— 是

Notes: Stone carvings depicting the scene of the Buddha's preaching Buddhist dharma.

↳ 浮雕展现神话叙事：

— 是

Notes: The dharma hall has brick carvings of the narratives of the Sixteen Princes from the Lotus Sutra.

↳ 浮雕展现人类/历史叙事：

— 是

Notes: Carvings of decorative boards on the roof depict varied scenes of literati activities.

↳ 其他【请注明】

—其他【请注明】: Carvings of the four heavenly kings on the wall of śarīra hall.

↳ 有其他绘画展现吗：

—是

↳ 他们是装饰板图画吗【可移动】

—是

Notes: The scrolls of paintings hung on the east and west wall of the śarīra hall.

↳ 他们是壁画吗：

—否

↳ 绘画展示了上帝在这里被崇拜：

—是

↳ 绘画展示了神话叙事：

—是

↳ 绘画展现了人类/历史叙事：

—否

↳ 其他【请注明】

—其他【请注明】：Paintings of the pagodas.

↳ 有马赛克呈现吗：

—否

↳ 铭文是装饰的一部分吗：

—是

↳ 有观赏性铭文吗：

—是

Notes: The calligraphy of plaques and stone inscriptions in the Ayuwang monastery.

↳ 有信息性/申明性的铭文吗

【比如历史叙事、日历、捐献者名单等等.....】

—是

Notes: The plaque of each building indicating its function.

↳ 铭文是官方的献词吗：

— 是

Notes: Plaques were bestowed by the imperial court in different historical times. For example, according to the *Ayuwang shan sheli baota ji* 阿育王山舍利寶塔記, the plaque hung above the śarīra stūpa in the śarīra hall has the title "Foding guangming zhi ta 佛頂光明之塔" written by the Emperor Gao 高 of Southern Song.

↳ 其他【请注明】

— 其他【请注明】：The antithetical couplet written on the pillars of each building.

↳ 其他种类的装饰

— 是【请注明】：Decorations for worshipping Buddhist divinities, for example, the streamers.

标志

这个地方有标志性的明显的特征吗：

— 是

Notes: Four stone pillars in the style known as Aśoka pillars were erected outside the front gate of the Ayuwang monastery.

↳ 眼睛（是否风格化）

— 否

↳ 超自然存在（动物化）

— 是

Notes: The design of Aśoka pillars has four lions sitting on the top of the pillar.

↳ 超自然存在（地球形状的）

— 否

↳ 超自然存在（拟人化的）

— 否

↳ 超自然存在（抽象的）

— 是

Notes: The pattern of dharma wheel on the Aśoka pillars.

↳ 死后世界/来世的画像

— 否

↳ 教义的不同方面（比如，十字，三位合一，密特拉符号）

— 否

↳ 人类

— 否

↳ 超自然存在叙事

— 是

Notes: The images of four lions, one elephant, one horse, one cow, one tiger, and four wheels represent the Buddha's preaching Buddhist dharma to the world.

↳ 人类叙事

— 是

Notes: The story of King Aśoka's establishing a series of pillars to publicize his edicts.

↳ 其他【请注明】

— 其他【请注明】: Inscriptions on the four pillars.

信念与实践

丧葬协会

这个地方是一个坟墓/埋葬地吗：

— 否

Notes: The Ayuwang monastery is not a burial site. However, in ancient times, revered monks were buried in the monastery. According to the Fozu tongji 佛祖統紀, the remains of Tiantai 天台 master Baoyun Yitong 寶雲義通 (927-988) were buried in the northwest area of the Ayuwang monastery.

此地是用来崇拜故人的吗：

— 否

Notes: The Ayuwang monastery was built for the worship of śarīra stūpa that preserved the Buddha's relics.

此地用于处理尸体吗：

— 否

坟墓/埋葬地有共同献祭：

共同献祭是坟墓/埋葬地的主要主任死亡导致的动物/人类献祭。

— 否

坟墓物品在场：

— 否

正式埋葬存在吗：

— 否

超自然存在

至上最高之神存在：

— 否

Notes: Divinities enshrined the Ayuwang monastery include Buddhas, Bodhisattvas, heavenly kings, five-hundred arhats, and guardian deities.

最高至上之神在此处和生灵交流：

— 未知领域

Notes: Main buildings of the Ayuwang monastery were designed for enabling Buddhist followers to make prayers and vows to the statues of Buddhist divinities. Accounts of spiritual responses document experience of communicating with the divinities and receiving divine aid.

以前的人类灵魂存在：

— 是

Notes: Buddhist rituals, for example, the Water-land ritual (shuilu fahui 水陸法會), were commonly held for providing salvation for the deceased and offering a rebirth in the Buddha's land.

可以看到人类灵魂

— 是

Notes: According to the Fozu tongji 佛祖統紀, in 723 CE a Tang-dynasty official Zilin 子璘 came to worship the śarīra stūpa in the Ayuwang monastery after his mother passed away. With the aim of eliminating his mother's sins, the official performed the kowtow forty thousand times. Miraculously, the spirit of his mother manifested in front of the stūpa and said she just gained a rebirth in the Trayastriṃśā.

人类灵魂可以被物理性感知：

— 未知领域

人类灵魂和此处的生灵沟通吗：

— 未知领域

Notes: According to the Xu gaoseng zhuan 續高僧傳, Buddhist followers once witnessed the miraculous scene of hundreds of monks circumambulating the śāriṃra stūpa at midnight.

非人类超自然存在存在：

— 是

Notes: The cult of a mystical eel in the Ayuwang monastery was prevalent since the seventh century. According to the Huta lingman pusa zhuan 護塔靈鰻菩薩傳, the eel was known as the Bodhisattva protecting the śāriṃra stūpa. It is believed that the eel accompanied the śāriṃra stūpa to Mount Mao 鄮 and dwelled in a well outside the Ayuwang monastery.

↳ 人类灵魂可以被看到：

— 是

Notes: According to the Huta lingman pusa zhuan 護塔靈鰻菩薩傳, when visitors brought incense and flowers to the well, they saw the eel swim in the water.

↳ 人类灵魂可以被物理性的感知：

— 是

Notes: Two accounts in the Huta lingman pusa zhuan 護塔靈鰻菩薩傳 described how the eel was caught by people who planned to boil it and eventually manifested divine power to return to the well.

非人类灵魂在此处和生灵交流吗：

— 是

↳ 在清醒的、每天的生活中：

— 是

Notes: According to the Yuanling miao daoyu ji 淵靈廟禱雨記, in time of drought, officials and Buddhist monks went to the eel to pray for rain. In 1166 CE, officials and monks went to the Yuanling temple to visit the eel with flowers, incense, and music. After the official made a prayer to the well, the eel appeared and went into the container. After that, the officials and monks brought the eel in the container to the Monastery of White Robe Avalokiteśvara in the capital of the prefecture and performed a rain-making ritual to receive rainwater successfully.

↳ 在梦中：

— 是

Notes: According to the Huta lingman pusa zhuan 護塔靈鰻菩薩傳, after the Wuyue ruler Qian Liu 錢鏐 (852-932) relocated the śāriṃra stūpa to his capital Hangzhou, he dreamed of a Bodhisattva wearing a crown of eels and holding two crabs under the arms. The king awoke from the dream and questioned the meaning of this dream. A Buddhist master answered that this bodhisattva was the eel in the well of Ayuwang monastery who came to Hangzhou to

protect the śarīra stūpa.

↳ 在催眠附身中：

— 否

↳ 通过占卜实践：

— 否

↳ 只通过宗教专家：

— 否

↳ 只通过君主：

— 否

↳ 其他

— 其他【请注明】：Manifest in the form of humans

Notes: According to the Huta lingman pusa zhuan 護塔靈鰻菩薩傳, in 869 CE, when a Buddhist monk came to worship the śarīra stūpa in the Ayuwang monastery, a child volunteered to serve as his attendant. After three years, the monk accomplished the rite of worshiping the śarīra stūpa. Then, the child told the monk: "I am the eel in the well. I was helping you show reverence for the śarīra stūpa."

混合人类-神圣的存在在场：

— 是

Notes: The statues of the divine monk Liu Sahe 劉薩訶 and the Daquan 大權 Bodhisattva are enshrined in the Ayuwang monastery. Liu Sahe is related to the founding myth of this monastery, while Bodhisattva Daquan is known as the guardian deity of Mount Yuwang (according to the Zenrin shōki sen 禪林象器箋). Bodhisattva Daquan can also be referred as the Zhaobao Qilang Daquan Xiuli Bodhisattva 招寶七郎大權修利菩薩. The statue of this deity wears the robe of Chinese official and has a unique pose of raising his right hand above his eyebrows as if he was gazing into distance.

↳ 可以看到混合人类-神圣灵魂：

— 是

Notes: According to the Eihei kaizan Dogen zenji gyojo: Kenzeiki 永平開山道元禪師行狀-建擲記, in 1227 CE, before Dōgen 道元 (1200-1253) returned to Japan, once he was copying the Biyan lu 碧巖錄, Bodhisattva Daquan xiuli came to offer him the light and helped him finish copying the book quickly.

↳ 可以物理性地感知混合人类-神圣灵魂：

— 是

Notes: According to the Zenrin shōki sen 禅林象器箋, Bodhisattva Zhaobao Qilang Daquan Xiuli 招寶七郎大權修利 is believed to be the son of King Aśoka who came to the Ayuwang monastery to protect the śarīra stūpa.

混合人类-神圣的存在和此地的生灵交流：

—是

在清醒的、每天的生活中：

—未知领域

Notes: The Zhaobao Qilang Daquan Xiuli Bodhisattva 招寶七郎大權修利菩薩 is also known as a seafaring deity protecting safe voyages for travelers at sea. Nowadays, in addition to the statue of this bodhisattva in the Ayuwang monastery, this bodhisattva can be found as the guardian deity in the monasteries of Sōtō Zen in Japan

在梦中：

—是

Notes: According to the Tokokuki 洞谷記, monk Kōei 琬瑛 dreamed of Bodhisattva Zhaobao Qilang 招寶七郎 entering the monastery and saying he followed the abbot's order to guard the gate of this monastery.

在催眠附身中：

—否

通过占卜实践：

—否

只通过宗教专家：

—否

只通过君主：

—否

其他

—其他【请注明】：Manifest as a white snake

Notes: According to the Eihei kaizan Dogen zenji gyojo: Kenzeiki 永平開山道元禪師行狀-建擻記, when Dōgen 道元 (1200-1253) boarded the ship that returned to Japan, a deity appeared on the ship and said "Master, my name is Nagas and Devas. In China, I am titled as Bodhisattva Zhaobao Qilang Daquan Xiuli 招寶七郎大權修利. Knowing that you received the patriarch's dharma seal and returned to your home country, I hope to follow you to protect the dharma." Upon Dōgen's request, this deity transformed himself into the shape of a small white snake

and stayed in Dōgen's food container.

超自然存在/至上之神以异国雕像的形式展现吗：

— 否

超自然互动

超自然监视存在：

— 未知领域

访客能和上帝或者超自然存在沟通吗：

— 是

↳ 访客能和上帝沟通吗：

— 未知领域

↳ 访客能和其他超自然存在沟通吗：

— 是

Notes: According to the Mingzhou Ayuwang shanzhi 明州阿育王山志, when visitors made prayers to the śarīra stūpa, sometimes they could see śarīra emerge as jewels on the top of the stūpa.

仪式与表演

仪式在这个地方发生吗：

仪式是一个或多个人为了宗教仪式而明显制定的行为。

— 是

↳ 大型仪式在此处进行吗：

— 是

Notes: For example, the contemporary Ayuwang monastery holds the Water-land ritual (Fajie shengfan shuilu pudu dazhai shenghui 法界聖凡水陸普度大齋勝會) that lasts seven days. In ancient time, according to the Fozu tongji 佛祖統紀, in 850 CE, eight thousand Buddhist followers in the Siming 四明 area came to worship the śarīra stūpa in the Ayuwang monastery. Miraculous responses occurred as flowers fell from the sky as snows and five-color light shone at night.

↳ 小型仪式在这里进行吗：

— 是

Notes: For example, rituals performed during monks' daily practices.

↳ 平均有多少参与者参加大型仪式：

— 请注明: more than 100

↳ 仪式多久发生一次：

— 请注明: Rituals were performed in the monastery every day.

↳ 有正统性检查吗：

— 未知领域

↳ 有正位检查 (orthopraxy checks) 吗：

— 未知领域

↳ 是否存在共时实践：

— 是

Notes: For example, during the rite of offering food to the hungry ghosts, one monk puts the offerings (commonly seen as a few grains of rice) on the stone pillar outside the Buddha hall while other monks chant the scriptures in the hall.

↳ 仪式中使用麻醉剂吗：

— 否

牺牲、祭品、和维护

此处有献祭表现

— 否

有自我牺牲展现吗：

— 是

↳ 自杀

— 是

Notes: According to the *Jingtu shengxian lu* 淨土聖賢錄, a monk named Zhenyuan 真緣 dwelled in the Ayuwang monastery in 1594. After seeing the śarīra stūpa emit light and manifest the image of the Buddha, he made a vow to burn his body as an offering to the śarīra stūpa. He applied oil on his body, sat cross-legged on the pile of firewood, and chanted the Buddha's name with his palms holding together. As the fire approached his body, other monks saw the light of five colors emit from his head and the golden image of Bodhisattva appeared in the light.

↳ 杀戮
— 否

↳ 损伤
— 是

Notes: According to the Zhongxing Fojiao ji Chan'an heshang zhuan 中興佛教寄禪安和尚傳, the monk went to the Ayuwang monastery and gouged out four holes as big as coins on his arms in front of the śarīra stūpa. After pouring lamp-oil into the holes, he lighted them as offerings to the stūpa. After that, he burned two fingers of his left hand as offerings to the dharma.

↳ 自我牺牲常见和/或是精英的要求：
— 否

物质祭品存在吗：

— 是

↳ 物质祭品是强制的吗：
— 否

↳ 物质祭品包括值钱物品吗：
— 是

Notes: Offerings placed on the table in front of the divinities' statues include sacred objects, for example, incense burners.

↳ 物质祭品包括日常生活物品：
— 是

↳ 物质祭品是否埋葬在此处（在贮藏处）：
— 否

↳ 其他

—其他【请注明】：Flowers and food, such as fruits and biscuits, are place on the offering table of the statues of divinities.

参加敬神/献祭活动是强制的吗：

— 是

↳ 由社群

— 是

Notes: The community of Buddhist monks demands monks to attend rituals regularly.

↳ 由特定个人

— 否

此处的维护表现吗：

— 是

↳ 是规定必须的吗：

— 是

↳ 有清扫吗（为了维护）：

— 是

↳ 是否有定期维修/重建：

— 是

↳ 是否由固定工作人员进行维护

— 是

↳ 其他

—其他【请注明】：Maintenance of the monastery is based on monastic codes.

朝圣与节日

朝圣是否存在：

— 是

Notes: The Prayer text written by Song dynasty pilgrims (宋人參詣医王山之時礼拜文) preserves the ritual text chanted by the pilgrims when worshipping the śārīra stūpa. During the twelfth century, a gathering named Lita hui 禮塔會 was prevalent in the Ayuwang monastery.

↳ 朝圣有多严格：

— 可选（常见）

↳ 朝圣是构建/建立场所的主要原因：

— 是

Notes: Pilgrimage is an important tradition for Buddhists holding the cult of śarīra stūpa.

↳ 朝圣到此处与重要的人生事件有关联吗：

— 是

↳ 出生

— 否

↳ 过渡到成年

— 否

↳ 死亡

— 是

Notes: The act of making a pilgrimage to the śarīra stūpa in the Ayuwang monastery to eliminate the sins of the deceased and bring them with a rebirth in the Buddha's land is commonly seen in historical records.

↳ 其他

— 其他【请注明】：The incident of experiencing the death of family members.

↳ 到此处的朝圣是否包括跟随建成的路线（道路）

— 是

↳ 这些路线与此地保持在一起：

— 是

此处是宴席的场所：

— 未知领域

节日展示吗：

— 是

Notes: Ceremonies are held in the Ayuwang monastery based on important dates on the Buddhist calendar, for example, the ceremony of bathing the Buddha.

↳ 节日的频次

— 请注明: Annual ceremonies.

- ↳ 社会的所有成员都参与节日吗：
 - 所有成员

- ↳ 节日是此处建筑物/装饰的一个决定因素吗：
 - 是
 - ↳ 要求对此处的特别维护/清扫
 - 是
 - ↳ 要求在此处的新的建筑体/装饰
 - 是
 - ↳ 要求维护/替换异教雕像
 - 是

- ↳ 平均来说，多少参与者会在此处聚集：
 - 数字: more than 100

- ↳ 宴席是节日的一部分吗：
 - 否

占卜与治愈

有占卜展示吗：
— 未知领域

治愈是否在此处展现/实践：
— 未知领域

机构和经文

宗教专家

宗教专家是否展现/掌控此地：
宗教专家是在人口群体中主要职责不是关心子女和手工生产，而是维护宗教图景和族群文化。

— 是
Notes: Buddhist monks.

↳ 全职
— 是

↳ 兼任
— 否

↳ 宗教专家是否特定性别
— 是

↳ 宗教专家是否特定种族
— 否

↳ 宗教专家是否属于特定阶级/
— 否

↳ 宗教专家是否致力于生活的地方
— 是

↳ 宗教专家是否在等级制度中分层：
— 是

Notes: The community of Buddhist monks include the abbot, monks in charge of different administrative work, and other monks.

↳ 是由这等级区分进入这空间的入口
— 是

Notes: When performing Buddhist rituals, the entrance used by monks differs.

此地给宗教专家容纳了生活空间吗：

— 是

Notes: The living area of the Ayuwang monastery has a dining hall, a kitchen, a hall of residence for monks, a hall for the visiting monks, a hall of residence for lay followers, and a storehouse.

这个地方被用作宗教专家的训练用吗：

— 是

Notes: The hall of dharma is for monks' daily Buddhist practices.

有正式的机构来维护此地吗：

由宗教社群或政治领袖授权的机构

— 是

Notes: The Buddhist Association of Ningbo.

官僚机构

有官方官僚机构在此处出现吗：

官僚机构包括一个主要涉及物质财富的会计和规则维护的等级制度。

— 是

Notes: The Ayuwang monastery is under the government of local authorities throughout its history.

↳ 官僚机构永久存在吗

— 是

↳ 官僚机构暂时/季节性存在吗

— 否

这个地方控制经济资源吗（土地，物品，工具）：

— 是

↳ 这控制了此地的主要支持收入吗

— 是

Notes: For the Ayuwang monastery, in premodern time, the profits of arable lands consisted a main portion of its income.

↳ 这个地方租赁土地吗

— 是

Notes: Historical records, such as the Mingzhou Ayuwang shan maitian ji 明州阿育王山買田記 and the Ayuwang shan Guangli chansi tutian ji 阿育王山廣利禪寺塗田記, describe the activities of lending the land to farmers, receiving arable lands through patronage, cultivating lands in the coastal area, and purchasing arable lands.

↳ 这个地方租赁工具吗

— 未知领域

公共事业

这个地方是否可以作为社区服务的场所：

— 是

Notes: The Ayuwang monastery provides the public space for social activities such as tourism, pilgrimages, and other religious gatherings.

↳ 公共食物分发和/或储藏
— 未知领域

↳ 公民职能的地方（人口普查，选举，其他）
— 否

↳ 司法实践的地方（审判，处决等）。
— 否

↳ 水管理功能
— 否

↳ 交通网络的部分
— 是

Notes: In ancient time, Buddhist monasteries located at the important line of communications provided accommodation for travelers on the road.

↳ 其他

— 其他【请注明】: According to the Yuwang shan Miaozhi chanshi taming 育王山妙智禪師塔銘, Miaozhi Congkuo 妙智從廓 (1119-1180) established five changsheng ju 長生局 to provide financial service.

文字/经文

此处是否保存了非宗教文字：

经济文档、记录等。

— 是

Notes: Inscriptions on stone steles preserved in the Ayuwang monastery, for example, the Chenkui ge ji 宸奎閣記 written by Sushi 蘇軾 (1037-1101). This building named Chenkui was built in the Ayuwang Monastery in 1070 to preserve the handwriting of Song emperors.

是否有与这个地方相关的经文

— 是

Notes: The Divine Spells and Great Dharanis Taught by the Seven Buddhas and Eight Bodhisattvas (Qifo bapusa suoshuo datuoluoni shenzhou jing 七佛八菩薩所說大陀羅尼神呪經) is commonly used by

Buddhists to worship the śarīra stūpa. The Ayuwang sheli baota bei 阿育王舍利寶塔碑 inscribed a section from this sutra describing the rite of prostrating oneself in front of the śarīra stūpa and chanting a special dhāraṇī eighty-one times to repent the past sins. The Aśokavadana that recounts King Aśoka's life is also relevant to the śarīra stūpa preserved in the Ayuwang monastery.

↳ 他们是被写下来的吗
— 是

↳ 他们是在这里被书写的吗
— 否

↳ 他们是口头的吗
— 未知领域

↳ 是否有与这个地方的起源和/或建筑有关的故事
— 是

Notes: The story of King Aśoka's dispersion of the Buddha's relics.

↳ 是否有负责解释经文的宗教专家
— 是

↳ 经文是建筑/地方的一部分吗
— 否

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